

Cytochrome P450
Proteins

Microbial metabolism in
diverse environments

GABA receptor

DNA
polymerase

Nucleoside
diphosphate
kinase
Solute carrier
family

Cytosolic
phospholipase

Glutamate
receptor

Mammalian
polyphospho-
kinase

Pathways

Biosynthesis of
secondary metabolites

Purine metabolism

Pyrimidine
metabolism

Caffeine
metabolism

Nicotinate

Sulfur
metabolism

Phenylalanine
metabolism

and
nicotinamide
metabolism

Biosynthesis
of
antibiotics

Fructose

and
mannose
metabolism

tyrosine
metabolism

acid
metabolism

Thymidylate
receptor

metabolic
degradation

Tryptophan
metabolism

Drug
metabolism
- other
enzymes

Arginine and
metabolism

tyrosine
biosynthesis

degradation

metabolic
degradation

Glycosaminoglycan
degradation

cytochrome
P450
metabolism

Styrene
degradation

Drug
metabolism

cytochrome
P450

metabolism

metabolic
degradation

metabolic
degradation

metabolic
degradation

metabolic
degradation

metabolic
degradation

metabolic
degradation

UDP-glucuronosyltransferase

Enzymes

DNA polymerase

